

Innovation Laboratory (InnoLab) approach to forest fire risk reduction: a successful story with forest communities living in fire-prone areas in Algarve, Portugal.

Social Innovation Research Group (SIRG), CiTUA – Centre for Innovation in Territory, Urbanism and Architecture, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisbon University.¹

Serra de Monchique and Serra do Caldeirão represent two forest territories in the Algarve region (southern Portugal) with a high risk of forest fires, affected with major social, economic and environmental impacts resulting from severe fires over the last few decades. Direct causes of increased risk, common to other at-risk territories in the country, include the concentration of forest mass in small and fragmented forest properties in a context of depopulation or ageing population, low dynamism in rural areas and devaluation of forest assets, leading to increased abandonment of forests and compromising effective fire risk management. In addition, indirect drivers should be addressed to improved resilience to forest fires in Portugal. Among such indirect drivers there is limited local capacity (financial and social resources) to effectively manage forests, low participation of local communities in decision-making processes and in forest related policy development such as the lack of participatory and collaborative approaches to promote the engagement and active role of local actors (municipalities, local authorities, forest producers' organisations and forest owners) from a community-based forestry perspective. Motivated to respond to this challenge, Social Innovation Research Group - SIRG (CiTUA/IST) developed an Innovation Laboratory (InnoLab) approach within the Bridge Project (Bridging Science and Local Communities to wildfire risk reduction)², that was applied in Monchique case study.

The InnoLab Bridge, a participatory and collaborative approach based on Strategic Thinking for Sustainability – ST4S (Partidário, 2021), aims to create collective spaces for dialogue and sharing of knowledges, visions and experiences involving multiples actors (public, private and community) to: i) facilitate social learning on key aspects of risk and vulnerabilities to forest fires, ii) build and enhance local adaptive capacities for risk reduction, iii) build bridges and strengthen the actors' network and collaboration in collective actions and iv) foster the active role of forest communities in decision-making process of forest territories focused on reducing forest fires risk. In Monchique, the InnoLab Bridge was developed between 2022 and 2024 and involved, in a set of participatory sessions, representatives of forest-related regional and national levels public agencies, municipal authorities, local entities/associations, forest producers' organizations, companies, private owners and residents.

The first InnoLab session in Monchique was a Participatory Mapping, a collaborative cartography method which allows visual and geographical expression of the reality perceived and lived by local communities through the spatial reproduction of their territory in a collaborative map, 'filtered' by their local experiences and perceptions. This participatory session represented a rich social practice involving forest owners with different characteristics and different interactions with the forest territories of Monchique. It enabled to identify and recognise the diversity of local knowledge, perceptions and actions in forest fire risk, and most importantly, it stimulated the mobilisation and involvement of the community of forest owners, placing them in an active role in the debate on forest fire risk management in their territory (Partidário et al, 2022). InnoLab then carried out a sequence of six participatory sessions, with a set of sequential purposes, with all the local actors: Vision, Priorities and Capacities, Roles and Responsibilities, Strategies for Action and, lastly, the development of an Action Plan tailored to the context and expectations of the local actors, built by the local group, which is now known as the Monchique Local Action Group (Dias et al, 2024).

¹ Contact: (+351) 218418321 - Joana Dias (joanafmdias@tecnico.ulisboa.pt) / Guilherme Saad (guilherme.saad@tecnico.ulisboa.pt)

² Bridge Project: for further information access <https://bridgecomunidade.pt/en> and https://zenodo.org/communities/bridge_community

Figure 1. Photographic archives of the InnoLab Bridge Participatory Sessions - Monchique, 2022-2024 (Bridge, 2024)

The vision participatory session, directed by the motto ‘What future do we want for the Monchique's forest?’, aimed to develop a collective vision for the forest to guide sustainable management strategies and fire risk reduction. This session was essential to create a community visioning for Monchique's territory and guide strategic priorities to be improved, and possible pathways to be followed and initiatives to be taken by the local group. It was followed by the Priorities and Capacities session, which aimed to discuss and define priority actions and identify local capacities (community and institutional) to guide strategies and actions to reduce the risk of fire. In this session, the local group defined three strategic priorities: 1) Promote the valorisation of the rural / forest areas, 2) Attracting young people to the municipality's rural areas and 3) Critically reviewing the legal and regulatory framework in force related to the management of forest areas. Based on the priorities and actions defined in the previous session, the following Roles and Responsibilities session addressed important aspects related to the roles and respective responsibilities of different actors in forest fire risk management, as well as identifying other key actors to be contacted and integrated into local group to enable each priority action.

The last participatory sessions (Strategies for Action) of the InnoLab Bridge were workshops to establish ‘clear action paths’ to enable interventions in the territory of Monchique, utilising existing local capacities and creating strategies to build the necessary actions. As a result, the group developed a more detailed Local Action Plan with a set of actions focused on “Valuing the rural/forest areas” and “Attracting young people to rural areas”. These two strategic axes were directly interrelated and considered to be direct interventions in the territory (i.e. ‘more practical’ actions) and more feasible given the current responsibilities and capacities of the Local Action Group. The strategic axis “Revision of the legal framework” was not included in the Action Plan as it fell out of direct action of the group in the Monchique territory.

Once the Local Action Plan was defined, the Social Innovation Research Group continued to support the local group in their journey to be committed and autonomous towards their Action Plan implementation. Thus, the team organised face-to-face and online meetings involving the members of the local group to provide support and orientation to ensure the effective implementation of the set of interventions in the territory included in the plan developed by them. Finally, it's worth noting that, during the initial phase of the process and concomitantly throughout all the InnoLab participatory sessions, a range of socio-educational activities were carried out aiming to involve the school community, in collaboration with the Group of Monchique Schools. This also allowed to spread the InnoLab Bridge through Monchique's community, having been developed diverse strategies for dissemination and communication of the InnoLab actions (e.g. social media posts, flyers, newsletters, releases

in local/regional media, videos, etc.) to promote and enhance local debate on forest fires and also to stimulate the participation of that community and their local representatives.

All this process with the Monchique Local Action Group faced challenges that had to be overcome. These include a strong local mentality of ‘blaming the other’ and ‘disbelief in change’, which made it difficult to involve and engage local actors, mainly at the beginning of the process. Also the low level of interaction, and sometimes conflicts between Monchique's forest owners, which is related to an attitude that is still very much marked by individualism and differences in interests, culture and language, namely between the national (Portuguese) owners and the ‘foreign’ owners, even these have lived in the region for many years. To overcome these barriers, the Social Innovation Group adopted different local engagement and awareness-raising actions (mentioned above), as well as conflict mediation and proximity communication strategies. All these strategies were fundamental to achieving the results obtained with the InnoLab, turning this narrative into a success story.

The main results achieved with the InnoLab have contributed significantly to address two major challenges in reducing the fire risk and promoting a sustainable and resilient development in Monchique's forest territories. The first challenge refers to the need to strengthen an actors’ network in Monchique as a contribution to promote social learning by sharing different visions, experiences and knowledge on key aspects of fire risk management and also to facilitate collaboration among different actors, both central aspects for collaborative and adaptive management to forest fires risk (Saad, 2022). Specifically in terms of strengthening the local actors’ network in Monchique, it’s noteworthy that the InnoLab involved 56 actors in participatory sessions, including 22 entities (11 of them local), 2 companies of pulp and paper sector and a total of 34 forest owners of Monchique, 26 nationals and 8 foreigners (Annex). The second challenge refers to the importance of increasing the adaptive capacity of the local community. The InnoLab created space to place the local community in an active role in forest management. It promoted the adoption of sustainable land use practices and created a Local Action Group that can become a vital partner in sustainable forest policy and planning in Portugal (Soares, 2023).

Both results are directly aligned with the guidelines of the National Integrated Rural Fire Management Plan (RCM, no. 45-A/2020). This called the attention and interest of the Integrated Rural Fire Management Agency (AGIF) in Portugal that allocated new resources to ensure the continuity of the InnoLab Bridge approach in the Algarve region. The contract (2024-2025) involved the Social Innovation Research Group (CiTUA/IST), University of the Algarve (UAlg), Intermunicipal Community of the Algarve (AMAL) and local municipalities enabling 1) the continuity and support for actions of Monchique Local Action Group and 2) extend the application of InnoLab approach to the Serra do Caldeirão, another forest area at high risk of fires in the Algarve.

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